

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Integrated service policy in the Surabaya main port area to achieve marine defense empowerment

Moh. Lukman Hakim *, Abdul Hakim, Lely Indah Mindarti and Hermawan

Faculty of Administrative Sciences, Brawijaya University, Malang Indonesia.

Global Journal of Engineering and Technology Advances, 2023, 17(01), 130–138

Publication history: Received on 05 September 2023; revised on 15 October 2023; accepted on 18 October 2023

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/gjeta.2023.17.1.0215>

Abstract

Harbor Order is everything that is related to the implementation of port functions to support the smooth, safe, and orderly flow of ship, passenger, and ship traffic. or goods, shipping safety and security, intra- and/or inter-modal movement, and encouraging the national and regional economy while still paying attention to regional spatial planning. Ports also carry out activities to provide port services, especially loading and unloading of goods and containers with appropriate increased volumes. This research aims to find an integrated service policy in the port area to achieve maritime defense empowerment. The type of research used is descriptive qualitative, with research analysis on policy implementation consisting of Content of Policy and Context of Implementation. Researchers also use the theory of Public Policy Implementation to establish a communication model for implementation analysis, with a very strong emphasis on what influences acceptance or rejection across layers of government. Data collection techniques using observation and interviews, and data analysis techniques using qualitative descriptive analysis follow four stages, namely data collection, data reduction, data presentation, and conclusions and verification. The results of this research are facts that:

- The performance process for loading and unloading activities at the Port of Surabaya is to support the empowerment of maritime defense areas has gone quite well,
- Performance results Loading and unloading activities at the Port of Surabaya to support the empowerment of maritime defense areas have been carried out well and can accommodate all port stakeholders.
- The most appropriate policy model to support the implementation of integrated port services is to implement.

The Integrated Port Policy for Service Excellent (IPPSE) or High Technology Based Port Area Synergy Regulations and improve the Security and Comfort of Superior Services at Ports to support the empowerment of Indonesia's maritime defense areas.

Keywords: Integrated Service Policy; Port; Regional Empowerment; Maritime Defense

1. Introduction

The National Port Order is a port system that contains the roles, functions, types, hierarchy of ports, National Port Master Plan, and port locations as well as intra- and intermodal integration and integration with other sectors. Government activities in ports include the following matters: regulation and guidance, control, supervision of port activities, shipping safety, and security. Port administration has the function of preparing operational work plans for port service activities together with government agencies. It also carries out airport ownership, ship safety, ship measurement, and registration, as well as maritime service activities (Cuadrado et al, 2004). Shipping is a unified system consisting of transportation in waters, ports, safety and security, as well as maritime environmental protection. Maritime economic activities include guiding services, channel services, container terminal goods stacking services, ship

* Corresponding author: Moh. Lukman Hakim

navigation services, and loading and unloading activities. Apart from the maritime service activities above, some maritime stakeholders have not been integrated in looking at issues regarding how to manage ship safety and security and protect the maritime environment in the waters of the Main Port of Surabaya, this needs attention in the implementation of integrated port services policy. There are several supporting factors, namely the existence of regulations, the availability of equipment and the availability of an adequate system. Meanwhile, several inhibiting factors include inadequate human resources, equipment, and technology, limited infrastructure including infrastructure and superstructure, insecurity, and disorderly implementation of operations in loading and unloading services resulting in operational delays in loading and unloading activities (Álvarez-SanJaime et al, 2015).

If there are inhibiting factors, corrective steps must be taken so that the loading and unloading process of the ship can take place smoothly, quickly, and on time. The Integrated Services Policy for Port Services must be implemented optimally by each port by paying attention to aspects of ship safety and security as well as maritime environmental protection. For this reason, it is necessary to develop a policy model which is a direction of action that has a purpose and is determined by an actor in overcoming a problem or problem, an action that leads to goals proposed by a person, group, or government in a certain environment in connection with the existence of certain obstacles while looking for opportunities to achieve goals or realize desired targets (Botti et al, 2017).

Based on the problems mentioned above, the problem statement in this research is how to develop an Integrated Service Policy for Port Services to Support the Empowerment of Maritime Defense Areas in Indonesia. The type of research used is descriptive qualitative, with research analysis on policy formulation consisting of Content of Policy and Context of Implementation. Researchers also use the theory of Public Policy Implementation to establish a communication model for implementation analysis, with a very strong emphasis on what influences acceptance or rejection between layers of government related to ports.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Public Policy Implementation

Several theories relate to variables that influence the implementation of public policy, one of which is Merilee S. Grindle's theory (2017). According to Merilee S. Grindle (2017), successful implementation is influenced by two large variables, namely content policy (content of policy) and implementation environment (context of implementation). These variables include the extent to which the interests of the target group are contained in the content of the policy, the type of benefits received by the target group, the extent of the changes desired from a policy, whether the location of a program is appropriate, whether a policy has mentioned its implementers in detail, and whether a program is supported by adequate resources. The Grindle model is determined by the content of the policy and the context of its implementation. The basic idea is that after the policy is transformed, then the policy implementation takes place.

Furthermore, according to Malcolm Goggin (1990) to advance a more scientific approach, as an implementation study, they established what they called a communication model for implementation analysis, with a very strong emphasis on what influences the acceptance or rejection of messages between layers of government. The next policy model was put forward by Daniel Mazmanian and Paul A. Sabatier (1983), who argued that implementation is an effort to carry out policy decisions. A policy implementation model with an implementation analysis framework (a framework for implementation analysis) is one of the appropriate policy implementation models and operational. According to them, policy implementation analysis identifies the variables that influence the achievement of formal goals throughout the implementation process (Ruan et al, 2018)

2.2. Strategic Management in Integrated Services

A public service organization that uses a strategic foresight model also focuses on developing specific areas of expertise or capabilities and developing cooperative efforts with other organizations that it believes will be necessary to ensure that the strategic vision is realized (Pallis & Vaggelas, 2005). This type of strategic management is associated with a form of intellectual leadership that is concerned with engaging the hearts and minds of managers and employees and securing their agreement to the established strategic direction. Foresight-based strategic models can be defined as being based on the idea of guiding strategic action using intelligence. This has philosophical echoes in the work of the pragmatists who reconciled being realistic with idealism. They suggest the importance of imagining a future that projects what is desired in the present and planning a path to that future (Hakim et al, 2023).

According to Hakim (2022) believes that, in the future, working through the strategic planning process will not happen as a "one-day affair" or as a joint effort". They argue that it is necessary for organizations to repeatedly work through

processes that lead to ongoing involvement in strategic management. Transformational strategic management draws attention to three challenges, namely: leadership, user empowerment, and cooperative efforts with its main partners in strategic management of integrated port services.

2.3. Logistics Management

In a broad sense, the scope of logistics management includes everything related to the transfer (distribution) to, from, and between Company facilities. Gerlitz and Meyer (2021) added that the logistics management carried out is more modern and integrated. Logistics management includes managing the distribution and storage of goods, spare parts, and finished goods from producers or suppliers to the company and then to customers strategically.

The military logistics system to support the empowerment of defense areas includes:

- Defense Logistics. Logistics is the bridge between the front line and the rear line, and the logistics process is an economic element in military operations. Defense logistics is all efforts to ensure policy, planning, organizing, implementation, supervision, and control through the development and use of personnel, material, facilities, and services according to operational demands, both in quantity, quality, time, type, location, and condition and can maintain its readiness during use (Leiren, 2015).
- Regional Logistics. Preparation of logistical support is determined by the location and distance from the defense terrain and areas of defense and resistance bases. Development Logistics support centers follow the location of economic and industrial development centers (according to the country's territorial layout) which combine political, economic, socio-cultural, and defense needs (Notteboom et al, 2022).

2.4. Research Thinking Framework

Figure 1 Research Thinking Framework

According to Grindle (2017), the policy implementation model is determined by the content of the policy and the context of its implementation and will be strengthened by implementation theory. public policy Goggin (1990), established a communication model for implementation analysis, with a very strong emphasis on what influences the acceptance or rejection of messages between layers of government, This is what is recognized as a system that will be created to obtain the best, integrated and sustainable service policy scenario, as well as reconstructing the factors that influence the achievement of formal goals throughout the implementation process with theory according to Mazmanian and Sabatier (1983). The policy scenario includes a model for integrating port services with Safety and security, Operations and environment, Maintenance and revitalization as well as improving public services, increasing the role of stakeholder cooperation, and improving the Port Terminal towards the expected ideal conditions. The following is a research framework model on the conditions of integrated port services:

2.5. Research Methods

This research is qualitative. Qualitative research in question is to understand the phenomena experienced by research subjects holistically by descriptive means in the form of words and language in a context, especially natural ones, by utilizing various natural methods. Furthermore, this research uses descriptive qualitative research which aims to collect detailed actual information that describes existing symptoms, identifies problems, or examines prevailing conditions and practices. The descriptive method is used to systematically describe certain facts or areas.

Operationally, the focus of this research is integration between *stakeholders* plays a role in port services , especially loading and unloading activities, security and order, safety and security of shipping as well as maritime environmental protection at Perak Port, Surabaya, Integrated service from *stakeholders in port services* , especially in loading and unloading activities, sustainable security and order, which can anticipate future developments in the dynamics of the governance system, as well as policies what is the best integrated service from the stakeholders (IDN Navy, Pelindo Regional III, Port Authority Office, Navigation District and Sea Transportation Service, Syahbandar/Harbormaster, Scouting, and Users) which can be implemented in port services, especially in loading and unloading activities, maritime security and order, shipping safety and security as well as sustainable maritime environmental protection to support the empowerment of sustainable maritime defense areas at the port of Surabaya .

2.6. Description of Research Location

Research description is an activity to provide a complete picture of the research area and is intended to explore and explain phenomena or realities at the research location and the surrounding maritime community environment by describing variables regarding the problem or unit under study. The research locus taken was the Port of Surabaya. The ports included in the integrated Master Plan for the Port of Surabaya and its surroundings include Surabaya Port and Teluk Lamong Terminal in Surabaya City, Gresik Port and Manyar Terminal in Gresik Regency, as well as Socah Terminal and Tanjung Bulupandan Terminal in Bangkalan Regency.

As the main port, the Port of Surabaya and its surroundings have a very strategic role and function, namely as a support for smoothing the flow of maritime transport traffic and as a driving force in increasing economic growth in East Java in particular and the Eastern Region of Indonesia in general. These roles and functions are very dominant and complement each other. Thus, the Surabaya Harbor hinterland and its surroundings cover mainly the entire area of East Java Province, and parts of Central Java province and the Special Region of Yogyakarta province. Apart from that, Surabaya Port is also a *transshipment* port for goods from the Eastern Region of Indonesia, both for international and domestic trade activities or vice versa.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Supporting and Inhibiting Factors for Implementing the Integrated Port Services Policy

The Integrated Port Services Policy to support the empowerment of maritime defense areas can be overcome through a policy that is competent for the success of the policy. In this section, we reconstruct a model of appropriate policy implementation and operations that influence the achievement of formal goals throughout the implementation process, indicators of theoretical and technical problems in implementation (Schepens et al, 2022)

Through discussion of research results, supporting and inhibiting factors for implementing policies for implementing Integrated Port Services from each agency and stakeholders above, research propositions can be formulated from the discussion, Supporting and inhibiting factors for the implementation of policies for the implementation of Integrated Port Services, especially in loading and unloading activities to support the empowerment of maritime defense areas, there are still problems, including:

- **Regulations and Policies**, in the absence of a supreme central decision-making institution, the effectiveness of implementing regulations and strengthening the regulatory structure in the field of maritime transportation needs to be improved by establishing a supreme central decision-making institution.
- **Infrastructure**, there are still separate container stacking locations. There is a need to improve the quality of port infrastructure, especially in several terminals at the port of Surabaya as a trade gateway to Eastern Indonesia.
- **Service Performance and Impact**, the problem of Guidance Shipping Flow which is not yet optimal which will affect, among others:
 - Safety and security performance needs to be improved through compliance with ship seaworthiness for all Indonesian-flagged vessels, both domestic and foreign shipping, as well as compliance with international shipping regulations.
 - The standard for achieving the dwelling time target is 3 - 4 days at Tanjung Perak port, which is still below the dwelling time standard in several neighboring countries such as Singapore, around 1 day, and Tanjung Pelapas (Malaysia) around 2 days.
 - High competition between modes, for inter-modal passenger movements The role of the sea mode is now starting to be competed with by the air mode, as for the movement of goods between countries islands (especially between Java-Bali-NTT) Sea mode is not yet able to fully compete with road mode.
- **Information Technology**, the Inaportnet system which has not been fully integrated, the effectiveness and efficiency of Technology and Information in the Internal Environment of the Surabaya Main Port Authority Office, as well as in the national shipping industry, in general, using the Inaportnet system and internal online applications which have not been accommodated by the Inaportnet system (Talley et al, 2014).
- **Human Resources**, the need to increase competency, especially for technical officers in the field and administrative officers related to project implementation in the Surabaya port environment. The policy related to the moratorium on CPNS recruitment limits the supply of human resources so that human resource needs at the Surabaya Main Port Authority office cannot be met. Infrastructure: There is a need to improve the quality of port infrastructure, especially in several terminals at the port of Surabaya as a trade gateway to Eastern Indonesia (Sutomo & Soemardjito, 2012).

3.2. Integrated Port Services Implementation Policy Model

So far, the implementation of Integrated Port Services at the Main Port of Surabaya still has several shortcomings and has not been fully implemented. Based on the findings explained above, an Integrated Service Policy Model for Port Services that is appropriate to be implemented or recommended at the Main Port of Surabaya is obtained, namely:

- Theoretical Foundations of Policy Models. **Integrated Port Policy for Service Excellent (IPPSE)**. Based on the findings of the empirical model and theoretical model above, an appropriate Integrated Service Policy Model for Port Services is obtained, namely by applying The new policy called *Integrated Port Policy for Service Excellent (IPPSE)*.
- Definition of *Integrated Port Policy for Service Excellence abbreviated as IPPSE is an Integrated port policy for superior service or it could also be a policy of "High Technology Based Port Area Synergy Regulation to support the Empowerment of Maritime Defense Areas to create security and superior service comfort at the Main Port of Surabaya"* which recommends the creation of legislation that refers to Government Regulation PP No. 31 of 2021 concerning the Implementation of the Shipping Sector.
- This policy model is recommended or proposed to maximize the Integrated Port Services policy that has been implemented at the main port of Surabaya.

Policy model *Integrated Port Policy for Service Excellence (IPPSE)* This also accommodates the Strategic Plan, namely *"Increasing Transportation Safety"*, namely by solving problems and maximizing Guide Services which depend on tides through the cooperation of PT. Indonesian Harbor and PT. Surabaya West Shipping Channel to dredge the shipping channel. This aims to maximize the process of ships entering and leaving the port without depending on the tides and preventing ship stranding accidents or leaks due to exposure to the shallow seabed. Apart from that, maximizing the Inaportnet system which will be integrated with all the data needed to carry out a voyage will be useful in ensuring the safety of ships and passengers. Having a system as a location for collecting ship safety documents such as Seaworthy Certificates, Safety Certificates, and Ship Crew and Passenger Registration Letters can prevent *Human Error* from not collecting shipping documents. The existence of this integrated system will facilitate the process of *tracing* passengers and ships if a ship accident occurs (Vaggelas & Pallis, 2010).

Policy model Integrated Port Policy for Excellent Service (IPPSE) will accommodate the *next Strategic Plan* namely *"Improving the Quality of Policy, Regulatory and Legal Governance"* through solving problems and increasing Supervision

and Implementation of Sanctions that are not yet strict by monitoring port law enforcement so that they can enforce the law firmly. Apart from that, the problem of Policy Makers that still exists in each agency is also resolved by collaborating between port institutions in creating and implementing policies that are aligned or the same in each institution to facilitate the process of implementing integrated service policies for port services, especially the loading and unloading process. The next problem that will be resolved is the problem of not having a supreme agency as a decision-making coordinator, namely by establishing a special institution tasked with determining policy decisions that will be implemented in all port institutions (Zen et al, 2022).

Policy model Integrated Port Policy for Excellent Service (IPPSE) This will also help implement the Strategic Plan, namely *"Increasing the Quality of Competent Human Resources"* through a policy of organizing periodic training for employees in all port institutions. Apart from that, a *recruitment* process policy is being formed which must be based on educational or training *background* that supports the employment process. The next Strategic Plan *"Improving the quality of environmentally friendly transportation"* is also implemented in the policy model Integrated Port Policy for Excellent Service (IPPSE) by maximizing the Inaportnet system which will be integrated with all the data needed for shipping, it will be useful in ensuring environmental safety. There is a system as a location for collecting ship safety documents such as Seaworthy Certificates, Safety Certificates and the baggage certificate carried by the ship can guarantee the seaworthiness of the ship so that it does not produce pollution to the water or air environment. Apart from that, maximizing the problem. Lack of attention in evaluating port equipment can be a means of ensuring that port equipment does not produce pollution from damage that occurs, for example, engine oil leaks which cause soil pollution.

The Next Strategic Plan is *"Increasing Control and Supervision"* which will be maximized with a policy model *Integrated Port Policy for Service Excellent (IPPSE)* through solving problems and maximizing Supervision and Implementation of Sanctions that are not yet strict, namely by implementing monitoring of port law enforcers so that they can enforce the law firmly. Apart from that, the optimization of the inaportnet system so that it can accommodate all existing requirements from each port institution also supports increased Control and Supervision, namely by monitoring shipping documents such as Seaworthy Certificates and Safety Certificates. which ensures the safety of ships and passengers as well as the environment. Policy model The Integrated Port Policy for Service Excellent (IPPSE) will also maximize the implementation of the next Strategic Plan *"Improving the Quality of Good Governance"* by resolving problems and maximizing Supervision and Application of Sanctions that are not yet firm by implementing monitoring of port law enforcers so that they can enforce the law effectively. Apart from that, problem-solving was also carried out, namely that the government had not completely resolved the problem of loading and unloading by evaluating the performance of Pelindo and other port institutions in carrying out port operations by the government as the highest authority. Then problem-solving is carried out. There is no highest agency as a decision-making coordinator by holding joint meetings between port institutions to form a special institution tasked with determining policy decisions that will be implemented in all port institutions.

3.3. Potential of Main Port as Supporting Port for Maritime Defense Area Empowerment

The existence of Government Regulation PP no. 31 of 2021 is expected to be implemented by all port *stakeholders* with the support of the new policy model Integrated Port Policy for Service Excellent (IPPSE) namely an Integrated port policy for superior service or it could also be a policy of High Technology Based Port Area Synergy Regulation to support the Empowerment of Maritime Defense Areas and to create security and superior service comfort at the Main Port of Surabaya, which includes ensuring, overcoming, supervising and even taking action against various problems and obstacles faced and can be integrated or integrated into an integrated port services service so that one unified system in shipping consisting of transportation on the water is obtained, ports, safety and security, and protection of the maritime environment. Matters that are integrated or integrated comprehensively include ports and shipping safety and security as stated in the policy of Government Regulation PP. No. 31 of 2021:

- Port is everything related to the implementation of port functions to support the smooth, safe, and orderly flow of ship, passenger, and/or goods traffic, sailing safety and security, a place for intra- and or inter-modal transfers as well as encouraging the national and regional economy while still paying attention to regional spatial planning.
- A terminal is a port facility that consists of a berthing pool and a place for ships to dock or moor, a place for piling up, a place for waiting and boarding and disembarking passengers, and/or a place for loading and unloading goods.
- Shipping Channels are waters which, in terms of depth, and width and are free from obstacles to other shipping, are considered safe and secure for navigation.
- Navigational Aids - Shipping means equipment or systems located outside the ship that are designed and operated to increase the safety and efficiency of ship navigation and/or ship traffic.

- Shipping Telecommunications is special telecommunications for the Shipping service which is any transmission, sending, or receiving of every type of sign, image, sound, and information in any form via wire, optical, radio, or other electromagnetic systems in the mobile Shipping service which is part of safety Cruise.
- The International Code for the Security of Ships and Port Facilities (International Ship and Port Facility Security Code), hereinafter referred to as the Code, is an international regulation that is an amendment to the 1974 Safety of Life at Sea Convention for the security of Ships and Port Facilities which consists of part A as an order and part B as a recommendation.
- The Port Security Committee, hereinafter referred to as PSC is a forum consisting of all relevant parties at the Port who are involved in handling Port security.
- Security Level is a classification of risks to Ships and Port Facilities according to the intensity or likelihood of Security Incidents that can occur after going through the observation and data collection process.
- Shipping Safety and Security is a condition where safety and security requirements are met regarding transportation in waters, ports, and the maritime environment.

4. Conclusion

Based on the results of the analysis and discussion previously described, conclusions can be drawn to answer the problem formulation and achieve the research objectives. The following are the conclusions of this research,

- The integrated service policy for port services following Government Regulation PP. Number 31 of 2021 concerning the Implementation of the Shipping Sector in the performance process of loading and unloading activities at the Main Port of Surabaya to support the empowerment of maritime defense areas, has been running quite well. This can be seen from the implementation of policies that can accommodate the interests of relevant stakeholders and increase the productivity of port activities. Implementing the integrated service policy on port services can provide benefits and positive changes that support port activities following the functions of each institution. The implementation of this program is supported by several ministries such as the Ministry of Transportation and the Ministry of BUMN, Class I Surabaya Navigation District, Surabaya Main Port Authority, Pelindo III Surabaya, Surabaya Scouting, Main Harbormaster, IDN Navy, and other institutions. However, regarding this implementation process, there needs to be a new policy that can support the smooth running of the integrated service process, such as the implementation of the Integrated Port Policy for *Service Excellent (IPPSE) policy*, which aims to ensure that if there is a discrepancy, the follow-up action taken will be appropriate and the application of the sanctions given will also be firm so that the implementation of the policy will be more optimal or it could also be by implementing the High Technology- Based Port Area Synergy Regulation policy which aims to utilize all technology related to existing constraints. can be integrated easily and can be known quickly by all related parties.
- The integrated service policy for port services by Government Regulation PP. No. 31 of 2021 concerning the Implementation of the Shipping Sector on the results of the performance of loading and unloading activities at the Main Port of Surabaya to support the empowerment of maritime defense areas, has been implemented well and can accommodate all existing port institutions with a level of compliance. high levels and speed up port activities. However, in its implementation, there are still shortcomings, especially in the flow of confirmation and coordination, which gives the impression of giving rise to an attitude of indifference among the parts involved, so it is necessary to hold joint activities between all relevant parts to improve communication and coordination between parts. Togetherness activities that can be carried out include gatherings between port institutions or non-formal activities such as casual chats during morning coffee.
- Several factors support the implementation of the integrated service policy for port services, especially in loading and unloading activities at the Main Port of Surabaya, namely the existence of regulations that support the implementation of the Integrated Service policy for port services clearly, where the regulation is Government Regulation PP. No. 31 of 2021 concerning Implementation of the Shipping Sector. The next supporting factor is the existence of the Inaportnet system as a Port Integration system. Apart from that, the existence of adequate sophisticated equipment at the main port of Surabaya will facilitate the process of implementing this policy. Apart from supporting factors, there are also factors inhibiting the implementation of integrated port services policies, such as the absence of a central decision-making institution which causes policy variations between port institutions, container stacking locations that are outside the port area so that distribution by land is needed to move gold boxes from the depo to the port or vice versa. The pilotage shipping route is not yet optimal because it still depends on the tidal conditions of seawater and the condition of shipping lanes which still contain sea mines. The Inaportnet system is not yet fully integrated into all ports in Indonesia. The Inaportnet system often experiences technical problems. The quality of Human Resources is not yet optimal, as indicated by delays that occur in the loading and unloading process.

- The most appropriate policy model in supporting the implementation of the integrated service's policy for port services is to implement the policy, namely Integrated Port Policy for *Excellent Service (IPPSE)* or it could also be a policy "High Technology Based Port Area Synergy Regulations to Support Superior Security and Comfort Services at the Port of Surabaya". From the implementation of this policy, several problems will be maximized from regulatory and policy aspects, infrastructure and facilities aspects, performance and impact aspects of shipping lane services, information technology aspects, and human resource aspects. Implementation of the Policy Recommendation Model, namely Integrated Port Policy for Excellent Service (IPPSE) will support the decision of the Head of the Surabaya Main Port Authority Office.

Future work

Based on the research that has been carried out, several future works can be used to develop several things, including:

- Management and maintenance problems are based on high technology, so that security and comfort can be achieved, especially in port services in the inaportnet system . which is integrated to support the empowerment of maritime defense areas as a space for the tools and conditions for fighting for the Indonesian nation.
- The government can develop and implement policies that can resolve the problems of developing docks, terminals, depots, silting up and shallowing of waterways that occur in the implementation of policies for implementing integrated services in high technology-based port services so that development plans such as the Teluk Lamong terminal are in line with the stages and the future. The conversion of the Mirah terminal into a maritime toll road terminal can be realized to support the empowerment of the maritime defense area as a space for the tools and conditions for fighting for the Indonesian nation.
- The government will continue to make efforts to improve the process and performance of implementing the Integrated Port Services policy so that port activities become faster, more effective, and more efficient.
- The policy model is one of the results of a diffusion of innovation. An innovation can easily enter a social system if the innovation can be accepted institutionally, and the institution determines it as part of the leader's policy. That is what is called institutionalization. The initial stage for researchers to carry out innovation diffusion is to introduce the policy model to all parties, especially related parties. Introduction can be through outreach, publications, seminars, etc. After the introduction, there is also a need for assistance to state holders if the policy model is adopted. Assistance can be achieved by holding training, workshops, and coaching.
- Each port institution can pay attention to the quality of competence of its employees by providing periodic training regarding work techniques or national insight.
- The government, especially the Ministry of Transportation, can formulate or revise regulations that hinder the implementation of integrated port services policies.
- Pelindo III will expand the area as an integrated container stacking depot so as not to cause congestion during the loading and unloading process.
- Pelindo III can synergize and collaborate with the Indonesian Navy and take part in efforts to empower the defense area, considering the importance of preserving the environment through mangrove conservation which is in line with one of the Regional Government programs so that there is a need for aquatic sports facilities in the Surabaya area and program development marine tourism.
- The further research can develop the results of this research by using other research objects such as airports and stations as well as adding expert informants related to the research object.

Compliance with ethical standards

Acknowledgments

The authors greatly acknowledge the support from **the Faculty of Administrative Sciences, Brawijaya University, Malang Indonesia** for providing the necessary resources to carry out this research work. The authors are also grateful to the anonymous reviewers and journal editorial board for their many insightful comments, which have significantly improved this article.

Disclosure of conflict of interest

The authors declared no potential conflicts of interest concerning the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article.

References

- [1] Álvarez-SanJaime, Ó., Cantos-Sanchez, P., Moner-Colonques, R., & Sempere-Monerris, J. J. (2015). The impact on port competition of the integration of port and inland transport services. *Transportation Research Part B: Methodological*, 80, 291-302.
- [2] Botti, A., Monda, A., Pellicano, M., & Torre, C. (2017). The re-conceptualization of the port supply chain as a smart port service system: The case of the port of Salerno. *Systems*, 5 (2), 35.
- [3] Cuadrado, M., Frasquet, M., & Cervera, A. (2004). Benchmarking the port services: a customer-oriented proposal. *Benchmarking: An International Journal*, 11 (3), 320-330.
- [4] Hakim, ML, Hakim, A., & Mindarti, LI (2023). Policy in the Port Services Industry for Regional Empowerment in Indonesian Maritime Defense. *International Journal of Professional Business Review: Int. J. Prof. Bus. Rev.*, 8 (7), 89.
- [5] Hakim, L. (2022, October). Implementation of Integrated Service Policy for Port Services to Support Empowerment Sea Defense Area. In *STTAL Postgraduate-International Conference (Vol. 6, No. 1)*.
- [6] Gerlitz, L., & Meyer, C. (2021). Small and medium-sized ports in the TEN-T network and nexus of Europe's twin transition: The way towards sustainable and digital port service ecosystems. *Sustainability*, 13 (8), 4386.
- [7] Goggin, M.L., Bowman, A., Lester, J.P., & Laurence Jr, J. (1990). *O'Toole. Implementation Theory and Practice: Toward a Third Generation*.
- [8] Grindle, M. S. (2017). *Politics and policy implementation in the Third World (Vol. 4880)*. Princeton University Press.
- [9] Leiren, M.D. (2015). Scope of Negative Integration: A Comparative Analysis of Post, Public Transport and Port Services. *JCMS: Journal of Common Market Studies*, 53 (3), 609-626.
- [10] Mazmanian, D.H. and Paul A. Sabatier. (1983). *Implementation and Public Policy*.
- [11] Notteboom, T., Pallis, A., & Rodrigue, J. P. (2022). *Port economics, management, and policy*. Routledge.
- [12] Pallis, A. A., & Vaggelas, G. K. (2005). Port competitiveness and the EU 'port services' directive: The case of Greek ports. *Maritime Economics & Logistics*, 7, 116-140.
- [13] Ruan, X., Feng, X., & Pang, K. (2018). Development of port service network in OBOR via capacity sharing: an idea from Zhejiang province in China. *Maritime Policy & Management*, 45 (1), 105-124.
- [14] Schepens, W., Ragsdale, D., Surdu, J.R., Schafer, J., & Port, R.N. (2002). The Cyber Defense Exercise: An evaluation of the effectiveness of information assurance education. *The Journal of Information Security*, 1 (2), 1-14.
- [15] Sutomo, H., & Soemardjito, J. (2012). Assessment Model of the Port Effectiveness and Efficiency (Case Study: Western Indonesia Region). *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 43, 24-32.
- [16] Talley, W. K., Ng, M., & Marsillac, E. (2014). Port service chains and port performance evaluation. *Transportation Research Part E: Logistics and Transportation Review*, 69, 236-247.
- [17] Vaggelas, G. K., & Pallis, A. A. (2010). Passenger ports: services provision and their benefits. *Maritime Policy & Management*, 37 (1), 73-89.
- [18] Zen, BP, Zafia, A., & Putro, INY (2022). Network Security Analysis Simulation at the GCS in the UCAV to support the Indonesian Defense Area. *RESTI Journal (Information Systems Engineering and Technology)*, 6 (5), 824-831.